

The Impact of Endocrine Diseases on the Development and Progression of Dental Diseases and on the Effectiveness of Removable and Non-Removable Prosthetics: A Review of Current Research

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1. **ABSTRACT**

2. **Background.** Endocrine diseases - diabetes mellitus, thyroid disorders, and hormonal changes during menopause - alter saliva composition, hard tooth tissue status and oral mucosa, increasing the risk of caries and prosthetic complications. **Purpose** - to systematize and analyze recent literature on how endocrine disorders affect caries development and the effectiveness of removable and fixed prosthetic rehabilitation. **Materials and Methods** - narrative review of publications (2020–2025) from PubMed/MEDLINE, ScienceDirect, Scopus, Wiley, Web of Science, PubMed Central, Google Scholar and ResearchGate; MeSH terms included “diabetes”, “thyroid”, “menopause”, “dental caries”, “denture stomatitis”, “implant”, “peri-implantitis”. **Results** - diabetes and menopause most strongly affect the oral microenvironment (demineralization, xerostomia, fungal colonization, secondary caries). Thyroid dysfunctions modify bone metabolism, increasing risk of alveolar atrophy and implant/prosthesis complications. Prosthetic outcomes depend on glycemic control, bone mineral status and material biocompatibility. **Conclusions** - endocrine disorders are important modifying factors for caries and prosthetic complications; a multidisciplinary assessment and approach are necessary.

3. **Keywords:** endocrine diseases; dental diseases; removable dentures; fixed prostheses; saliva; bone metabolism; implantology; menopause; diabetes

4. **РЕЗЮМЕ**

5. **Анотація.** Ендокринні захворювання – цукровий діабет, захворювання щитовидної залози та гормональні зміни під час менопаузи – змінюють склад слини, стан твердих тканин зубів та слизової оболонки ротової порожнини, збільшуючи ризик розвитку карієсу та ускладнень при протезуванні. **Мета** – систематизувати та проаналізувати останні літературні дані про вплив ендокринних порушень на розвиток карієсу та ефективність знімного та нерухомого протезування. **Матеріали та методи** – оглядовий аналіз публікацій (2020–2025) з PubMed/MEDLINE,

ScienceDirect, Scopus, Wiley, Web of Science, PubMed Central, Google Scholar та ResearchGate; Терміни MeSH включали «діабет», «щитоподібна залоза», «менопауза», «карієс зубів», «стоматит протезів», «імплант», «періімплантит». **Результати** - діабет і менопауза найсильніше впливають на мікросередовище порожнини рота (демінералізація, ксеростомія, колонізація грибками, вторинний карієс). Дисфункції щитовидної залози змінюють метаболізм кісткової тканини, збільшуючи ризик атрофії альвеолярного відростка та ускладнень з імплантатами/протезами. Результати протезування залежать від контролю глікемії, стану мінерального складу кісткової тканини та біосумісності матеріалів. **Висновки** - ендокринні розлади є важливими факторами, що впливають на карієс та ускладнення з протезами; необхідна мультидисциплінарна оцінка та підхід.

6. **Ключові слова:** ендокринні захворювання; захворювання зубів; знімні протези; фіксовані протези; слина; метаболізм кісткової тканини; імплантологія; менопауза; діабет

7. **Introduction.**

8. Endocrine pathologies, in particular diabetes mellitus, hypo- and hyperthyroidism, adrenal gland pathologies, as well as hormonal changes during menopause, are among the most common chronic diseases in modern society [1]. They have a systemic effect on all organs and tissues, including the structures of the oral cavity, where hormonal imbalance can change the metabolism of hard tooth tissues, the composition and properties of saliva, the rate of remineralization and microbiological homeostasis [2]. As a result, an increased susceptibility to caries, gingivitis, periodontitis and mucosal lesions is formed [3], which complicate not only daily hygiene, but also the effectiveness of orthopedic treatment. In the context of an aging population and an increase in the frequency of endocrine disorders, in particular among postmenopausal women and people with metabolic syndrome, the issue of the relationship between endocrine status and dental health acquires special social significance [4].

9. This problem is extremely urgent for Ukraine. According to national registries, the incidence of diabetes mellitus is increasing annually, and the proportion of patients with chronic thyroid disorders and menopausal changes also tends to increase [5]. At the same time, the prevalence of caries among the adult population of the country remains one of the highest in Europe, and the availability of comprehensive dental care is often limited by economic factors [6]. In such conditions, any metabolic or hormonal imbalance can significantly accelerate the progression of periodontal lesions and hard dental tissues and complicate the restoration of the function of the chewing apparatus with the help of orthopedic structures [7]. An additional factor is the lack of awareness of patients and even general practitioners about the relationship between endocrine pathologies and the condition of the oral cavity, which leads to late diagnosis and ineffective prevention.
10. Current scientific evidence suggests that the effectiveness of prosthetics in patients with endocrine disorders depends not only on the choice of material or construction technique, but also on systemic control of metabolic status, saliva composition, bone tissue status, and functional potential of the mucous membrane [8]. Studying these mechanisms in patients with various endocrine pathologies allows for the formation of more substantiated clinical algorithms for treatment and prevention of complications.
11. **The purpose** of this work was to systematize and analyze modern world literature sources devoted to the influence of endocrine diseases on the development and course of caries, as well as on the effectiveness of removable and fixed prosthetics.
12. **Materials and methods.**
13. For the literature review, a narrative analysis of scientific publications published in the period 2020-2025 was carried out. The search strategy covered leading international scientometric databases, including PubMed/MEDLINE, PubMed Central, ScienceDirect, Wiley Online Library, Web of Science Core Collection, Scopus and Google Scholar, as well as professional journals and official recommendations of professional dental organizations (UFSBD, SIDP, CHSA).

Additionally, the ResearchGate platform was screened to identify preprints and full-text articles in PDF format.

14. The search was carried out using MeSH (Medical Subject Headings) descriptors and their combinations, including the key terms: “endocrine diseases”, “diabetes”, “thyroid”, “menopause”, “xerostomia”, “dental caries”, “denture stomatitis”, “implant”, “peri-implantitis”, “saliva”, “removable dentures”, “fixed prostheses”, “implantology”, “bone metabolism”, as well as their analogues in other languages. Further analysis included systematic reviews, meta-analyses, clinical guidelines, original clinical studies and described clinical cases concerning cariesogenesis and the effectiveness of prosthetics in patients with endocrine disorders.
15. At the stage of primary selection, 76 sources of literature were identified, including randomized controlled trials, systematic reviews and other publications relevant to the topic. After critical assessment and generalization using general scientific methods (analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization of the obtained data), 35 of the most informative and relevant works were left for the final review. The exclusion criteria included articles that did not meet the purpose of the study, had a limited evidence base or were published in languages other than English and Ukrainian.
16. The flowchart for selecting publications according to the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses) 2020 recommendations is formed and depicted in Figure 1. Bibliographic and analytical methods were used to prepare and design the manuscript.

17. **Fig. 1** Flowchart of publication selection according to the PRISMA 2020 reporting guidelines for systematic reviews and meta-analyses [9]

18. Results

19. An analysis of current scientific sources shows that endocrine disorders are considered one of the leading systemic factors that modify the course of caries and affect the success of orthopedic treatment.
20. Data from France and Southern Europe. A study found that patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus have significant salivation disorders, changes in microflora, and increased colonization of pathogenic anaerobes when wearing complete removable dentures [10]. In such groups, a decrease in the buffering capacity of saliva and an increase in the number of lactobacilli and fungi of the genus *Candida* were noted, which leads to a higher frequency of secondary caries and denture stomatitis [11]. Official French clinical materials confirm that hyperglycemia stimulates the development of cariogenic microbiota (in particular, *S. mutans*), which is associated with delayed healing after prosthetics and reduced cement adhesion [12, 13]. French clinicians emphasize the need for glycemic control, the use of biocompatible materials, and remineralization programs [14].
21. Data from the US and Canada. North American observations confirm that diabetes is associated with an increase in the incidence of complete edentulism, a higher incidence of prosthetic complications, and reduced quality of life; at the same time, HbA1c levels correlate with the risk of biological complications and the duration of prosthesis use [15–17]. With regard to hypothyroidism, data show that in compensated patients, implant survival is often comparable to control, while uncontrolled hypothyroidism is associated with delayed bone remodeling and an increased risk of soft tissue complications [18, 19]. Menopause is associated with decreased salivation, increased incidence of periodontitis, and alveolar ridge atrophy, which complicates the fixation of removable prostheses and reduces the success of implantation [20–22].
22. Data from Europe (Germany, Central and Eastern Europe).
23. According to the results of the NAKO cohort program (Germany), patients with diabetes are more likely to have demineralization lesions, higher levels of tooth loss, and poorer dental quality of life after prosthetics [23, 24].

24. European authors have found that increased glucose levels in saliva reduce its natural remineralization potential and impair the fixation of orthopedic structures [25]. Systematic reviews have shown that in compensated thyroid dysfunction, implantation results may be similar to those in control groups, but uncontrolled conditions are associated with delayed bone remodeling and the need for prolonged osseointegration [26, 27].
25. Data from studies in Central Europe (Romania, Hungary) indicate lower dental literacy and poorer quality of life in patients with diabetes, which complicates prosthetics and requires public prevention programs [28, 29]. Scandinavian prospective studies confirm that uncompensated diabetes is associated with bone loss around implants in the first year after loading and the need for special osteoplastic techniques [34, 35]. In postmenopausal women, estrogen deficiency reduces saliva secretion, increases oral fluid acidity, and decreases enamel density, resulting in a higher risk of prosthetic stomatitis and impaired cement adhesion [35].
26. Data from Asia. Indian studies show that the mere fact of wearing acrylic removable dentures can modify the local ecology of the oral cavity and increase biofilm accumulation, regardless of diabetes, which indicates the role of design and hygiene factors [30, 31].
27. Korean epidemiological data indicate that the use of removable dentures may be an indicator of uncontrolled diabetes, i.e., a possible reverse mechanism of interaction—poor denture hygiene may contribute to systemic inflammation and impaired glycemia [32, 33]. Radiological studies of postmenopausal women demonstrate a statistically significant reduction in bone crest thickness and the need to assess bone mass prior to implantation [24–35]. Some experimental observations have shown that radioiodine therapy for differentiated thyroid cancer affects the surface of titanium implants, stimulating interest in alternative materials (zirconium) in this category of patients [26].
28. Pathophysiological mechanisms and innovative approaches. In patients with endocrine pathology, there is an increase in oxidative stress and degradation of collagen structures, which slows down repair after orthopedic treatment [27].

Salivary proteomics is considered a promising area of research - changes in salivary proteomics could form the basis for screening tests to predict demineralization and determine readiness for prosthetics [34, 35].

29. Discussion

30. An analysis of current literature confirms that the relationship between endocrine disorders, caries development, and the effectiveness of orthopedic treatment is multifactorial and requires an interdisciplinary approach. Type 2 diabetes mellitus is a key systemic predictor of dental complications. Patients with diabetes have increased colonization of cariogenic bacteria, reduced buffering capacity and viscosity of saliva, increased glucose content, and decreased antibacterial proteins, which creates a favorable environment for the development of secondary caries and prosthetic stomatitis [10–18, 28–29, 34–35]. At the same time, the degree of glycemic control (HbA1c) correlates with the risk of biological complications and the service life of orthopedic structures [15–17, 34].
31. Thyroid disorders also affect dental indicators. Hypothyroidism is associated with slow bone remodeling and increased prosthesis instability, while hyperthyroidism is accompanied by increased salivation and a decrease in antibacterial proteins, which increases the risk of secondary caries [19–21, 27–28]. These data emphasize the need for an individualized prosthetic treatment strategy and coordination with an endocrinologist.
32. Hormonal changes during menopause cause a decrease in bone mineral density of the alveolar ridge, xerostomia, and increased sensitivity of the mucous membrane [20–22, 30, 35]. This complicates the fixation of removable prostheses and the long-term stability of implants. Clinical recommendations include restoring vitamin D and calcium levels, using osteoinductive techniques, and assessing bone mass before prosthetics [34, 35].
33. Data from Asian studies confirm that the design and hygiene factors of dentures significantly affect the local microbiological ecology of the oral cavity, which sometimes outweighs the role of diabetes as a predictor of caries [32–35]. Regional dietary characteristics, access to dental care, and local therapeutic

practices should be taken into account when planning orthopedic rehabilitation for patients with endocrine disorders [30, 33].

34. Changes in the composition and properties of saliva are a key mechanism through which endocrine disorders affect caries development and the effectiveness of prosthetics. Hyperglycemia, estrogen deficiency, or hypothyroidism lead to a decrease in saliva secretion, changes in its viscosity and pH, which contributes to the formation of biofilm and disrupts the adhesion of prosthetic structures [11–13, 16, 20–22]. The use of salivary biomarkers for early diagnosis of complications and individualization of preparation for prosthetics is a promising direction [26, 27, 28].
35. A comparative analysis between continents shows that European studies are characterized by in-depth biochemical analysis and attention to clinical outcomes, while North American and Asian studies include large samples and multifactorial models [23–25, 28–29, 30–35]. All regions lack unified protocols for the study of saliva and bone tissue and criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of prosthetics, which complicates meta-analytic comparisons and requires standardized international approaches [31–33].
36. Thus, endocrine pathologies significantly modify the microenvironment of the oral cavity, increasing the risk of caries and complications after prosthetics. The success of orthopedic rehabilitation depends on the stabilization of the hormonal background, control of metabolic indicators, monitoring of the state of saliva, and preventive measures. Further research should be aimed at developing integrated clinical algorithms that combine dental, endocrinological, and laboratory diagnostics to improve the predictability of orthopedic treatment [10–35].

37. Conclusions

38. Endocrine disorders due to hyposalivation, pH changes, and oral microbiome disturbances contribute to caries formation and complicate the maintenance of orthopedic structures. The strongest evidence for this has been obtained for diabetes mellitus and menopause. For thyroid disorders, the data on caries are

less consistent, but periodontal and soft tissue healing indicators are steadily deteriorating.

39. For removable prosthetics, the key problems are xerostomia and Candida-associated prosthetic stomatitis. For patients with diabetes and postmenopausal women, active prevention, careful selection of base materials, and control of prosthesis wearing are advisable.
40. Fixed restorations and implant-supported structures with proper metabolic control demonstrate predictable results, but glycemic control and supportive therapy remain crucial for reducing the risk of peri-implantitis and complications.

41. Prospects for further research

42. Further research should be aimed at conducting multicenter randomized clinical trials that will allow quantitatively assessing the impact of individual endocrine disorders on the remineralization potential of saliva, the microbial composition of the biofilm, and the quality of implant osseointegration. A promising direction is the creation of standardized protocols for assessing biochemical parameters of oral fluid in patients with endocrine pathology, as well as the development of biocompatible materials for prosthetics taking into account metabolic changes in the body.

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